

It's all in your head: The role of intellectuals in transition processes, a neo-Gramscian approach

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Abstract:

Antonio Gramsci's work has recently been used to explain why socio-technical transitions are not taking place. This literature builds on the Gramscian concepts of *transformismo*, passive revolutions, or war of positions. Gramsci's work can be insightful for transition scholars as he analyzed why transitions did not take place, as well as what the conditions for a transformation would be. For Gramsci, a transformation was preliminarily an intellectual endeavor. Only when the intellectual war (the war of positions) was won, could a physical war (a war of maneuver) be victorious. Thus, philosophy, ideology, beliefs, or folklore are the arenas that decide upon the success of a transformation. Accordingly, using a neo-Gramscian approach, changing people's worldviews is a vital factor for a successful transformation towards a sustainable society.

Intellectuals can have a key role in transformative processes as they can help to maintain or birth new worldviews. There is an increasing call for scientists to collaborate with stakeholders and actively contribute to transition processes. This is understood to be in contrast to scientists' traditional role as objective observers who are separate from society. However, using a Gramscian approach, it is obvious that scientists can be class-bound and thus influence societal trajectories and transitions. Understanding the role of scientists within transition processes might, thus, be valuable. This requires amongst others understanding the dynamics between individuals and social groups, as well as, the role of worldview or paradigm changes.

Within dominant transition theories, such as socio-technical transition theory, worldview changes do not take center stage. Furthermore, they do not shed light on the dynamics between individuals and groups. To address this shortcoming, I developed a novel transition concept. It enriches the adaptive cycle developed by Gunderson and Holling (2002) with neo-Gramscian thought. The novel transition concept helps to understand the dynamics between individuals and (counter hegemonic / hegemonic) groups, as well as the role of worldview changes in transition processes. Thus, it can help to understand how intellectuals, such as academics, can impact transformation processes.

1. Introduction

Evidence continues to mount indicating that human societies need to transform to be sustainable. Societies are overshooting six out of nine planetary boundaries (Richardson et al., 2023). Some projections show that we will likely not meet the Paris Agreement of keeping average global temperatures below 2°C (Rafferty et al., 2017). Biodiversity loss has reached a worrying magnitude (Cowie et al., 2022). Pollution (e.g. plastic and e-waste) remains a concerning problem (Bakhiyi et al., 2018; Borrelle et al., 2020; MacLeod et al., 2021; Odjegba et al., 2020).

While technological innovation will be relevant to tackling these environmental issues, they are insufficient as a stand-alone means. The chances to successfully tackle climate change will for example also depend on socio-economic conditions (Rogelj et al., 2018). Literature on pollution highlights the need to reduce the overall creation of waste streams (Bakhiyi et al., 2018; Borrelle et al., 2020). Apart from the need to raise recycling rates, consumption has to decline. Similar results emerge from research on greenhouse gas emissions. As sufficient absolute decoupling of greenhouse gas emissions from GDP growth seems out of reach, researchers indicate that alternative pathways (i.e. reducing consumption) need to be explored (Haberl et al., 2020). Suggestions to reduce consumption connect to concepts such as dematerialization, sufficiency, or minimalism. (Jungell-Michelsson & Heikkurinen, 2022; Lorek, 2014; Sarkar, 2022). Within the current economic system renouncing consumption leads to recession and is thus not an aspired solution (Alexander, 2012; Schneider et al., 2010). Accordingly, some suggest installing a new economic system in which human well-being is not primarily linked to GDP. Alternative economic systems are captured by research on steady state economies, post-growth, or degrowth (Asara et al., 2015; Daly, 1996; Jackson, 2021).

Degrowth is a social and academic movement. The social and academic spheres are not separate but in regular exchange. The most recent example is the Degrowth Assembly taking place prior to the 10th International Degrowth Conference in Pontevedra (International Degrowth Network, 2024). The conference as well as the Degrowth Assembly are not targeting people in a specific role, e.g. activist versus academic, but people in their various roles. The Degrowth Assembly is a “[...] space for degrowthers, activists, practitioners, researchers, artists, IDN [International Degrowth Network] members, and allies [...]” (International Degrowth Network, 2024). The conference invites and encourages collaboration among academics, local civil society, and activists (Post-Growth Innovation Lab, 2024b). This is not a new development, the International Degrowth Conferences always served as a platform for academic-activist discussions (Schulken et al., 2022). Apart from this bigger event, degrowth scholars are active in degrowth organizations that are spread over the world (Demaria et al., 2013; Schulken et al., 2022). This blurring of roles has been discussed in sustainability transition literature (Wittmayer & Schapke, 2014), where academics transcend *traditional* roles and become change agents. By this, they are no longer objective and neutral but potentially take a position and become subjective.

The socio-economic system that degrowthers envision is substantially different from the current socio-economic system (Demaria et al., 2013; Schulken et al., 2022). This raises the question of how a transformation from the current to a substantially different system

could occur (Barlow et al., 2022). A reflection of such a deep transformation is rather hypothetical as it is an ex-ante thought experiment. To shed light on how a deep transformation to degrowth could unfold I make use of a) transition theory and b) political economy literature. For the former, I employ socio-ecological transition theory, and for the latter neo-Gramscian thought. Neo-Gramscian thought is suitable as for Gramsci a revolution was in the first place an intellectual battle that required the collaboration between intellectuals and civil society. Intellectuals are strictly speaking not only academics¹. However, for this analysis, the notion of intellectuals will capture academics. The collaboration between intellectuals and civil society is key to challenging hegemony and initiating change. Using neo-Gramscian thought illustrates that science and society are not as separate as it might be perceived. The connection between academia and civil society is a feature of the degrowth movement.

Some frame the transformation to degrowth as part of a broader socio-ecological transformation (Barlow et al., 2022). Apart from this conceptual connection, socio-ecological transition theory is suitable as the adaptive cycle (which will be outlined below) includes a release phase (*collapse*), which is vital for transformations to take place. Furthermore, socio-ecological transition theory highlights the role of worldviews, beliefs, or values for change. This allows us to combine neo-Gramscian thought with it. However, a downside is that the illustrations of transformative processes render it difficult to reflect on the role of individuals within systems. To accommodate for this, a new illustration has been developed.

This paper aims to provide a framework that allows to reflect on how a deep transformation to degrowth could take place. It thus, also allows us to hypothesize on strategies the degrowth movement has to focus on.

2. Neo-Gramscian thought

Antonio Gramsci was an Italian intellectual and political activist who was in 1928 incarcerated by the Fascist regime for his political activities. In prison, he continued writing down his thoughts on social transformations (Jones, 2006). His prison notebooks provide interesting hypotheses about why transformations are not taking place and what conditions could support a transformation to take place. His work is rich, and many aspects could be used to understand contemporary dynamics relevant to the much-needed sustainability transformation. For example, several authors have used neo-Gramscian thought to explain why a deep transformation is not taking place² (Ford & Newell, 2021; Levy & Egan, 2003; Newell, 2018; Szabo, 2022).

This article focuses on how a transformation could take place. In line with Gramsci's ideas, the mutual relationship between intellectuals and civil society is understood to be key to a degrowth transformation. To understand the arguments made, several concepts will be introduced (intellectuals, base and superstructure, historical bloc, hegemony,

¹ For Gramsci everyone is or could be an intellectual as every work requires intellect (Martin, 2023; Femia, 1981).

² This literature explores the concepts of *war of positions* and *trasformismo* to understand how ongoing transitions are coopted by the hegemonic bloc. By successfully engaging in a war of positions and using the *trasformismo* strategy superficial changes are made to maintain hegemony.

civil society). Gramsci's ideas will then be paired with the adaptive cycle and applied to the degrowth movement.

2.1. Hegemony

For Gramsci hegemony is a continuous process of establishing and maintaining non-violent "intellectual and moral leadership" (Femia, 1981, p. 24). Hegemony is different from *dominance* and *coercion* which imply the employment of some degree of violence or force (reward and punishment). Hegemony secures social control "[...] by molding personal convictions into a replica of prevailing norms" (ibid.). Hegemony is thus characterized by a dominant worldview or ideology informing individuals' behavior (*practice*) and thoughts (*common sense*).

Through an *economic compromise*, the dominant class makes certain concessions (e.g., social welfare) to appease the non-ruling classes (Im, 1991). This economic compromise though, transcends the mere economic and must include ideology, values, and beliefs (ibid.). As hegemony is mostly a non-violent process, it relies on people's agreement to ideologies, values, or worldviews (e.g., that an economy needs to grow to secure well-being). Accordingly, means to spread and solidify worldviews are vital for this process. Here the role of popular culture, education, or religion becomes apparent (Femia, 1981). The agreement with the dominant ideology might, though, only be superficial. People might hold other values and worldviews, which they suppress³. Gramsci argued that the non-dominant class needs to suppress their own beliefs as they are unable to present their own beliefs as a structured, coherent ideology (ibid., p. 44). As we will see this is how intellectuals are relevant for revolutionary processes.

A successful revolution (transformation) needs the reversals of hegemony which is not simply the replacement of one hegemony with another one. "The principle of hegemony must itself be transformed – from a principle that mystifies the social situation to one that exposes exploitation and supersedes it" (Femia, 1981, p. 53).

2.2. Base and superstructure

Hegemony is reflected in the economic base, ideological superstructure, and civil society that connects the two spheres.

The ideological superstructure describes the ideology that dominates within a society throughout a certain period. The ideology is understood to be provided by and thus in alignment with the interests of the ruling class. Through institutions such as education, religion, art, and legislation ideology is disseminated through civil society (Jones, 2006). The economic base represents the economy, thus the means of production (tangible and intangible, human workforce and material means of production), how production is structured and organized (Jones, 2006).

Base and superstructure are in a dialectic relationship. The economic base determines what ideologies are possible. "The economic base sets, in a strict manner, the range of possible outcomes, but free political and ideological activity is ultimately decisive in determining which alternative prevails. There is no automatic determination: only the creation of a more or less favorable atmosphere for the diffusion of a new ethos." (Femia,

³ It has to be suppressed as disobedience with the hegemonic system can lead to repercussions (punishment, social exclusion, economic exclusion, etc.)

2016). At the same time, the hegemonic ideology is reflected in the economic base of a society. Thus, what and how things are produced are a reflection of the hegemonic worldview (Femia, 1981).

The historical bloc is “[...] a composite of distinct class and social forces joined politically and culturally under a specific form of hegemony” (Martin, 2023). Thus, irrespective of class those who share (ruling class) or belief in (non-ruling class) a specific ideology are part of one historic bloc. The mutual interaction and alignment of base and superstructure at a certain point in time is what Gramsci called the historical bloc (Im, 1991; Jones, 2006; Levy & Egan, 2003).

Civil society⁴ is part of the ideological superstructure with institutions therein replicating the ideology to secure hegemony (Femia, 1981; Jones, 2006). As part of the superstructure, civil society is too in a dialectic relationship with the economic base. In contrast to Marxist thought, Gramsci suggested that base and superstructure are in mutual exchange, determining each other. Thus, Gramsci did not think that the economic base determines the superstructure, but that ideology can influence the set-up of the economy. Furthermore, this perception allows for some leeway within superstructural institutions. For example, the educational system might be a means to spread alternative ideologies (Jones, 2006). Thus it is within civil society where transformations are made possible through the transformation of values, beliefs, and worldviews (ibid.).

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the social system: The arrows illustrate interactions within the system. Practice and common sense are in a dialectic relationship. Institutions are influenced by the

⁴ Gramsci distinguishes between the civil and the political society. The political society exerts coercive or other forms of forceful power through e.g. police and military. These kinds of power are understood to be less important in modern societies to establish and maintain social order. However, the political and the civil society are in close exchange. For example, military interventions are backed up by ideological support.

superstructure and they influence practices and common sense. In turn practices and common sense influence institutions and the superstructure. If all these layers are in alignment we find a historical bloc.

3. Intellectuals

Various institutions within a society serve to create hegemony by proliferating the dominant worldview (Femia, 1981). Among those is the educational system, including academia. As noted initially, this article focuses on intellectuals limited to the educational system, specifically to academia.

Given the importance Gramsci places on the proliferation of ideas in maintaining or establishing a new hegemony, it is not surprising that intellectuals have a special place in Gramsci's writing. Gramsci was firm in the "belief that intellectuals are the group most responsible for social stability and change; it is they who sustain, modify, and alter the modes of thinking and behavior of the masses" (Femia, 1981, p. 130).

Gramsci's conception of intellectuals negates characterizing intellectuals as objective, neutral, and independent⁵. On the contrary, the education system (including academia), like all other institutions of civil society, is political (Martin, 2023; Rose & Rose, 1976a). Intellectuals can be framed as translators between different spheres of society. Applied to Figure 1, they are part of institutions of civil society, are engaged with and reproduce the economic base, and can connect common sense with ideology.

3.1. Intellectuals as translators

Those in power as well as those who are not yet in power need intellectuals as translators. The translation capacities of intellectuals can be employed by the ruling class to proliferate their ideology. Likewise, the translation capabilities can also be used by the non-dominant classes to establish a new hegemony (see Figure 2).

Gramsci summarizes the former as follows:

"We have established that philosophy is a conception of the world and that philosophical activity is not to be conceived solely as the 'individual' elaboration of systematically coherent concepts, but also and above all as a **cultural battle to transform the popular 'materiality'** and to diffuse the philosophical innovations which will demonstrate themselves to be 'historically true' to the extent that they **become concretely** – i.e. historically and socially – **universal**. [emphasize added]" (Gramsci, 1999, p. 347).

Hegemony is a process that secures dominance through the adoption of a specific ideology by the masses. Influential traditional intellectuals can be used to create and maintain ideological support of civil society (Adamson, 1980, p. 149; Martin, 2023). That is facilitated by translating the ideology into common sense (Adamson, 1980, p. 149; Femia, 1981). Common sense is "the conception of the world which is uncritically absorbed by the various social and cultural environments in which the moral individuality of the average man is developed" (Gramsci, 1999, p. 343). For example, many people will

⁵ This might seem to contradict with the below-introduced categories of traditional and class-less intellectuals. However, we need to consider the historicity of those categories. Traditional intellectuals appear to be neutral, but that is because they represent the accepted ideology. Hence, they also subscribe to a specific worldview. Though, the normativity of that worldview might be neglected.

know that the economy must keep growing to avoid a recession and job losses (Büchs & Koch, 2019). This has become a common sense. Gramsci distinguishes between formalized, structured knowledge (*philosophy*) and unstructured knowledge (*common sense*). Civil society holds common sense, intellectuals can form and share structured knowledge (e.g. via the education system) (Gramsci, 1999; Martin, 2023).

Since the transformation is mostly an intellectual endeavor, alternative ideas need to be born and proliferated. Although alternative ideas can form within the realm of common sense, these ideas are too diffuse to challenge the hegemonic superstructure. Therefore, intellectuals are needed to translate an alternative common sense into a coherent, structured ideology that can challenge the hegemonic ideology on a superstructural level (Femia, 2016; Im, 1991; Martin, 2023). This intellectual war (war of positions) is not only carried out in day-to-day life but also in the intuitions of civil society. Accordingly, a revolution in society will be reflected in a revolution within academia⁶ (Femia, 1981, p. 105). Furthermore, the counter-hegemonic movements might profit from intellectuals who can find common ground among various movements and organize them to form a collective *force* (Im, 1991). Additionally, the discourse needs to be held using the symbols and terminology that have been coined and proliferated by the hegemonic system. Intellectuals might have the needed skills to navigate means of communication to challenge the superstructural ideology (Im, 1991).

Gramsci understood that ideology and common sense determine thinking and behavior. Thus, thought and action are united. These two are dialectically connected and can bring about a new ideology (Martin, 2023). Thus, creating a new ideology is not just a thought experiment but deeply rooted in day-to-day life and experience. Gramsci called the correspondence between action and thought philosophy of praxis. Aligning the two is “[...] a form of politics, not an abstract science” (Martin, 2023).

Figure 2: two-way translation

3.2. Politics and intellectuals

As scientists are part of the educational system, which is part of civil society, so are scientists too part of the dialectics between base and superstructure. Neo-Marxist

⁶ Efforts to diversify economics curricula to also include post-growth ideas are just one example. Another one would be in the field of agriculture where alternative paradigms push through (Kassam & Kassam, 2021).

literature explains that science and art are ideological and political (Rose & Rose, 1976a). The connection between the education system and the superstructural ideology can also be observed in the commercialization and privatization of this system (Bauwens et al., 2023; Morales-Doyle & Gutstein, 2019; Rose & Rose, 1976b). Through these processes the educational system not only proliferates the dominant ideology, it also partakes in the recreation of the economic base⁷ (Ciccotti et al., 1976; Gorz, 1976). Neo-Marxist literature also indicates that the portrayal of science as neutral was a maneuver to disguise the real-world (political, environmental, social) implications of scientific activity (Rose & Rose, 1976a).

Prominently Funtowicz and Ravetz (1993) called for the establishment of post-normal science that should (re)connect science with society. The arguments used by Funtowicz and Ravetz (1993) to explain the disconnect between science and society resemble arguments used by Gramsci (1999) to explain the disconnect, namely social stratification, thus class society. Funtowicz and Ravetz (1993) express their concern about science remaining in the hands of “power-politics,” which is why they advocate for the involvement of all relevant stakeholders. Similar to arguments in neo-Marxist literature on the political economy of science (Rose & Rose, 1976b), Funtowicz and Ravetz (1993) argue that science was depoliticized by hiding behind *neutral* statistics and technology. Post-normal science in contrast is “[...] a new scientific method, which does not pretend to be either value-free or ethically neutral” (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993).

3.3. Intellectuals in transformation processes

Gramsci differentiated between two main categories of intellectuals; traditional and organic (Adamson, 1980, p. 143f.; Femia, 1981; Martin, 2023; Olsaretti, 2013). The traditional category encompasses the independent, neutral objective scientist. In contrast to this, organic scientists can be affiliated with societal classes and their ideologies (Olsaretti, 2013). Class is here not limited to economic class but refers to any variable that separates individuals into groups within a society (e.g. gender, ethnicity, political orientation, worldview, etc.). The dialectic between traditional and organic intellectuals is reflected in the aforementioned call for post-normal science as well as the debate about the role of scientists within (sustainability) transformations (Bulten et al., 2021; Wittmayer & Schapke, 2014). Scientists acting as change agents are organic intellectuals. Even more so, as what a sustainable society looks like is a normative question (Caniglia et al., 2023; Horcea-Milcu et al., 2019) and can thus not be steered by objective, neutral scientific means⁸.

A special case of traditional intellectuals are completely detached researchers, who only know but do not feel. These researchers might form their own *caste* (Gramsci, 1999, p. 350; Olsaretti, 2013). Gramsci argues that to form a historical bloc, intellectuals need to connect with the civil society to feel and understand their problems and experience (Gramsci, 1999, p. 350). Furthermore, he points out that change happens by intellectuals connecting with the environment they try to influence in one way or the other. In consequence, “[the] environment reacts back on the philosopher and imposes on him a

⁷ By e.g. creating workforce that fits the economic base but also by adopting capitalist dynamics in the system (e.g. performance measured in productivity, publish or perish, or work that is stripped of ownership and creativity by producing knowledge for someone else)

⁸ Which is why Funtowicz & Ravetz (1993) postulated the establishment of post-normal science.

continual process of self-criticism. **It [the environment] is his ‘teacher’** [emphasize added]” (Gramsci, 1999, p. 348f.). “The unity of science and life is precisely an active unity, in which alone liberty of thought can be realized; it is a master-pupil relationship, one between the philosopher and the environment in which he can draw the necessary problems for formulation and resolution” (Gramsci, 1999, p. 349). Accordingly, intellectuals who can support a transformation from the bottom up need to connect with their environment in a reciprocal, co-creative, and non-hierarchical manner. The co-creation between intellectuals and people is decisive for transformative processes as through the exchange new concepts can emerge:

“[T]he most important [problem] of which can be subsumed in the form and the quality of the relations between the various intellectually qualified strata; that is, **the importance and function which the creative contribution of superior groups must and can have in connection with the organic capacity of the intellectually subordinate strata to discuss and develop new critical concepts.** [emphasize added]” (Gramsci, 1999, p. 341)

Gramsci assigned intellectuals a dynamic character where intellectuals can switch from organic to traditional and vice versa (Olsaretti, 2013). This dynamic character indicates their decisive role in transformation processes. Thus, to understand transformation processes it is necessary to understand the role of intellectuals in a) distilling new concepts through the exchange with non-ruling classes, b) translating the concepts into a coherent, structured ideology that can challenge the hegemony (see the bottom-up path in Figure 2).

Figure 3 illustrates the dynamic roles of intellectuals in transformation processes. The blue band captures the dominant hegemony. Traditional intellectuals (bluish dots) support the superstructural ideology of this particular hegemonic system. Through exchange with the environment, some intellectuals will start to challenge the ideology and form a new one. These intellectuals represent organic intellectuals (pinkish triangles) who connect to non-dominant classes in civil society. The organic intellectuals will connect with each other and potentially, a new hegemony will be established based on the new ideology. If this happens the organic intellectuals become traditional intellectuals of the new system (Martin, 2023; Olsaretti, 2013). As noted above, the establishment of a new hegemony is not simply a project of intellectuals. Rather intellectuals fulfill a critical role in equipping the non-ruling classes with discursive and political power (Carstensen & Schmidt, 2016). Thus, traditional intellectuals, who have been trained within the system that aligns with the hegemonic ideology, need to split from their traditional role and become organic intellectuals. Furthermore, “[...] as a class matures into a position where it can begin to assert its power politically, it becomes increasingly important to supplant traditional with organic intellectuals” (Adamson, 1980, p. 144).

Applied to the hegemonic capitalist system, traditional intellectuals commit to neoliberal capitalist economics. While they are now traditional intellectuals, before the capitalist system became hegemonic they were organic intellectuals (Femia, 1981, p. 130).

Figure 3: Intellectuals in transformation processes

3.4. Strategies in transformation processes

Gramsci distinguished between two main strategies to bring about a transformation, the war of maneuver and the war of position. The former constitutes a frontal attack against the hegemonic system. Gramsci theorized that modern (democratic) systems are too complex for a frontal attack to be successful (Femia, 1981). The superstructural ideology functions as the glue of the historical bloc. Without dissolving the glue, a frontal attack will not prove successful. In contrast, a war of positions is a slow-moving, long-term strategy to undermine the existing ideology and build and spread a new one (Femia, 1981; Im, 1991). To do this, the non-hegemonic class has to 1) uncover the flaws of the hegemonic ideology (i.e., the contradictions within the system), 2) provide an alternative

ideology (including common sense), and 3) provide actionable alternatives (practices, economic base). Furthermore, Gramsci highlighted the need for alternative groups to find common ground, unite, and together engage in the war of positions (Im, 1991). The war of positions constitutes a dialectic between destruction and creation. While the old is dismantled (discredited) the new is created (cognitively and practically) (ibid.).

At the same time, the establishment and expansion of an alternative ideology will not be successful if the hegemonic system is not in some form of crisis related to the economic base. Hegemony is a process that involves an economic compromise. If the ruling class is not able to make concessions, people's loyalty to the ideology will decrease (Im, 1991). In times of deep environmental crisis, the economic compromise includes concessions pertaining to environmental protection and reparation.

A transformation can be avoided by the hegemonic class through the application of specific strategies. First, if circumstances increase controversies about the hegemonic system, the non-ruling classes might demand change. In response, the hegemonic class can provide an adapted economic compromise. This strategy constitutes a *passive revolution*, which involves a change of the economic structure without a deeper transition of the superstructural ideology (Im, 1991; Martin, 2023). Apart from offering certain concessions, the ruling class can also make use of, *trasformismo*, a strategy that is more targeted toward shallow ideological changes. *Trasformismo* refers to coopting and absorbing alternative ideas that could challenge the hegemonic system (Morton, 2018; Newell, 2018).

4. Socio-ecological transition theory

Socio-ecology offers a transition theory via the concepts of the adaptive cycle and the Panarchy (Gunderson & Holling, 2002). First, these concepts will be outlined, then they will be connected to Gramsci's work. To accommodate the connection, an adaptation of socio-ecological transition theory will be presented that better reflects certain dynamics within the transformation process.

The adaptive cycle (see Figure 4) consists of four phases, exploitation (r), conservation (K), release (Ω), and reorganization (α). The transitions from the r to K and from the Ω to α phases are slow, whereas the transitions from the K to Ω and from the α to r phases are fast processes. The axes, potential and connectedness, capture changes along the adaptive cycle. From r to K connections within a respective system increase and become stronger. Potential can be read as options a system has at a specific point in time. It is built up between the r and K phases. Thus, by accumulating more assets, skills, knowledge, connections, etc. one has more potential in the K-phase compared to the r-phase. Although a system has more potential in the K phase it is also more likely to undergo a major change (through release and reorganization). Approaching the peak of the K phase, the system becomes more rigid and, thus less resilient to shocks (Gunderson & Holling, 2002).

The adaptive cycle illustrates transformations as sequential, where the release is followed by the emergence of something new(ish). This view has its roots in ecology, where for example plants regrow after a winter (Hollings, 1986). This illustrates that the adaptive cycle not necessarily leads to a transformation. Whether a system adapts or

transforms depends on the magnitude of the disruption (K to Ω) as well as the remaining potential and connectedness after the release.

Figure 4: Adaptive cycle: adapted from Gunderson and Holling (2002, p.34)

If we looked at the adaptive cycle in isolation, we could assume that a transformation is triggered solely by internal processes. However, the adaptive cycle is embedded in a multi-scalar system called Panarchy (see Figure 5). The Panarchy indicates that transformation processes are triggered by other connected adaptive cycles (*revolt*). Furthermore, a transformation can also be postponed or halted through panarchical connections (*remember*). The transformation process within the adaptive cycle as well as with the Panarchy relates to the concept of resilience⁹, which will not be further expanded on in this manuscript.

In this article, the focus lies on supporting, rather than hindering change. Therefore, the emphasis lies on the *revolt* and not the *remember* path. It needs to be highlighted that Figure 5 is schematic and thus, the *revolt* connection could play out in different stages of the connected system. A *revolt* can be triggered by a crisis of a subsystem (release phase) or by the subsystem having reached enough strength (conservation phase) to revolt. Similarly, the timing of the revolt with respect to the higher-order system matters. Thus, is the higher-order system close to a crisis point or rather stable when the revolt hits?

⁹ Further reading Olmos-Martínez & Ortega-Rubio (2020), Walker et.al (2004), Walker (2020).

The axes in Figure 5 indicate that higher-order systems are *bigger* and change slowly, while lower-order systems are *smaller* and change quickly. To grasp the difference, one could think of changing an action, versus changing a habit, versus changing a lifestyle.

Figure 5: Panarchical connections: adapted from Gunderson and Holling (2002, p. 75)

4.1. Gramsci and Socio-ecological transition theory

Gramsci's thoughts about social change resemble what Gunderson and Holling (2002) write about the special features of the socio-ecological system. In contrast to pure natural systems, socio-ecological systems can change in unexpected ways. Humans' cognitive abilities can speed up, delay, block change, or divert history in completely new paths. This overlaps with Gramsci's rejection of scientific Marxism, which assumes that human systems follow natural laws that would allow one to predict the future. In contrast, Gramsci thought that it "[...] is impossible to predict any determinate outcomes because outcomes depend on human decisions, which are not themselves determined by their antecedent conditions" (Femia, 1981, p. 77). Thus, he rejected deterministic views of social change by emphasizing the role of human consciousness.

Applying Gramsci's ideas to the adaptive cycle, the r to K phase is the period in which hegemony is established and maintained. The hegemonic system will be more vulnerable

to change if certain conditions are met: 1) the hegemonic system is unable to make a satisfactory economic compromise, and 2) the superstructural ideology is not sufficiently accepted by the non-ruling classes (Im, 1991). While a war of positions could occur already in the r phase, it is more likely that it is happening in the K phase (see Figure 6). Societal agreement to establish the new hegemony (r phase) will not provide sufficient ground to also establish a strong opposition¹⁰. Opposition might grow over time if the establishing hegemony is unable to meet the two above-mentioned conditions.

Figure 1 indicates that the social system is multi-layered. Thus, one adaptive cycle alone is insufficient to understand the dynamics. Figure 7 illustrates two scales with the lower scale capturing a united alternative that conducts a war of positions. As mentioned above, ideally the alternative is mature (in the K phase) and the hegemonic system is close to the release phase. This is indicated by Gramsci pointing out that the counter-hegemonic forces need to exhibit leadership before the counter-hegemonic forces have claimed power (Im, 1991).

Figure 6: Applying the war of positions to the adaptive cycle

¹⁰ A struggle between various alternatives might play out in the Ω to α phases. However, the r phase marks the point where one alternative has emerged as the winner. This alternative will from this point forward work on increasing its dominance.

Figure 7: Applying the war of positions to the Panarchy

While the Panarchy depicts the dynamics of a multi-scalar system, it remains difficult to imagine the dynamics between the scales through time. To this end, a new illustration has been developed.

4.2. An alternative depiction

Due to the spatial distance between adaptive cycles within the Panarchy depiction, one could have the impression that sub-systems are separate from an overarching system. However, they are not. Environmental economics, ecological economics, resource economics, etc. are all subdisciplines within the field of economics (with overlaps with other fields). Thus, they are all subsystems within the overarching system, the field of economics. While ecological economics might disagree with several aspects of mainstream economics, it is still situated within the field of economics (and other fields such as environmental sciences). Another problem of the Panarchy illustration is that one might get the impression that the interaction between different scales is punctual. The interaction between a subsystem and the overarching system is not a one-point-in-time instance, but continuous. Thus, the revolt is not a single instance, but a continuous dynamic between system and subsystem. Furthermore, a subsystem consists of further subsystems. For example, a subdiscipline consists of researchers devoted to the specific subdiscipline. Each individual can be framed as another adaptive cycle that impacts its

higher-order system (the sub-discipline). Hence, we have to imagine the adaptive cycle as a set of nested systems with continuous interactions between them.

Figure 8: Transition process

Figure 8 illustrates this nested adaptive cycle. It resembles Figure 3 but contains more detail. Figure 8 depicts three different scales, 1) the overarching hegemonic system, 2) groups, and 3) individuals within the overarching hegemonic system. The blue band indicates the hegemonic system. Within it are (groups) of individuals who align with the

system¹¹. As they align with it, they have the same color and are located centrally. The hegemonic system also contains (groups) of individuals who disagree with the system. These have a different shape and color and are located at the fringe of the system. If those non-aligning individuals form a group, they can engage in a war of positions in which they continuously challenge the hegemonic system. The idea of a revolution starting within the hegemonic system aligns with Gramsci's work, suggesting that a socialist revolution starts within the capitalist system (Im, 1991; Levy & Egan, 2003).

The band illustration fits Gramsci's idea about individuals' commitment to the hegemonic system (Femia, 1981). Femia (1981, p. 45), summarizes that the degree of the commitment depends on a respective person's socio-economic situation, thus the degree to which one can benefit from the economic compromise. "In Gramsci's conception, where a man falls on the continuum between absolute commitment and total rejection is intimately related to his socio-economic conditions" (Femia, 1981, p. 45). Accordingly, the band illustrates this continuum, with a central position representing absolute commitment.

Figure 8 contains the phases of the adaptive system indicated by the letters r, K, Ω , α . The war of position starts between the r and K phase. Prior to the war of positions, individuals (front runners) move from agreement to rejection, thus to the fringe of the band. This process is illustrated by a change in color, shape, and position within the band. Furthermore, individuals who disagree with the hegemonic system connect with each other and form groups (accumulation of pinkish triangles). These groups form an alternative common sense, practices, and finally an alternative philosophy (pinkish band within the blue band). Thus they form their own historical bloc within the hegemonic system (Im, 1991). By sufficiently challenging the hegemonic system, the blue band enters into the release phase. If the alternative system has become strong enough it might be able to determine the new system in the reorganization and exploitation phase.

It has been pointed out that base and superstructure are in a dialectic connection, where the "*base determines what forms of consciousness are possible*" (Femia, 1981, p. 121). The x-axis in Figure 8, only shows two ideologies (the hegemonic and one alternative). Though, several alternatives might be possible. Which of the possible alternatives (if any) follows the release phase is not set in stone (Femia, 1981, p. 121 f.).

5. The degrowth movement

Degrowth is a "democratically deliberated absolute reduction of material and energy throughput, which ensures well-being for all within planetary boundaries" (Schulken et al., 2022, p. 11). As this requires a fundamental restructuring of the socio-economic system, degrowth is not limited to reducing GDP. Rather it advocates ending the focus on GDP growth and instead focusing on diverse sources of wellbeing¹² (Buch-Hansen & Nesterova, 2023; Kallis et al., 2014). Moreover, degrowth is a cultural revolution that requires the decolonialization of the imaginary (Latouche, 2014).

¹¹ The position of the elements within the band connects to resilience theory by Walker et al (2004). Given the limited space, I cannot expand on the resilience aspect.

¹² Sharing, simplicity, care, cooperation, etc.

The themes captured by the degrowth movement are decades old. The term *décroissance* was potentially first mentioned in 1972 by the philosopher and political ecologist André Gorz (Demaria et al., 2013; Schulken et al., 2022). The degrowth notion was born in the atmosphere of increased environmental awareness, as 1972 also marks the year in which the *Limits to Growth* report was published (Meadows, 2010; Meadows & Meadows, 2007). The limits to growth have also been a core topic of ecological economics, where Nicholas Georgescu-Roegen provided foundational work in the 1970s. The mathematician and economist concluded that degrowth would be the logical result of an economy embedded in a biophysical reality that does not permit continuous economic growth (Baykan, 2007).

In the late 1900s and the 2000s the degrowth movement started to expand in France, Spain, and Italy (Demaria et al., 2013; Schulken et al., 2022). It seemed to have started in Lyon (France) in connection to other social movements around mobility and food security (Demaria et al., 2013). Journals and magazines (e.g., *Silence*, *Casseur de pub*, *La Décroissance*) dedicated to degrowth were vital to the spread of the ideas (Baykan, 2007; Demaria et al., 2013). The English term degrowth was for the first time officially used at the first International Degrowth Conference in 2008 in Paris (Demaria et al., 2013; Schulken et al., 2022). In 2024 the 10th International Degrowth Conference will take place in Spain. Since the beginning, these conferences have been a platform for activist-academia exchange (Schulken et al., 2022). This exchange is also practiced at the 10th conference (Post-Growth Innovation Lab, 2024b). Another example of this exchange is the book *Degrowth & Strategy*. Part two of the book is co-written by academics and activists. “The interrelations between theory and practice are at the core of the book, as no theory prepares us sufficiently for the creativity needed for building strategy, and strategy without theoretically informed considerations risks being reduced to short-term objectives without a vision” (Schulken et al., 2022, p. 30).

Several sources describe that the academic degrowth movement grew out of the social degrowth movement (Demaria et al., 2013; Engler et al., 2024). Though, looking at the historicity of the movement it seems as if they grew in conjunction and that the movement formed out of social, environmental, and economic concerns that were voiced by civil society and scientists long before the degrowth movement took shape. Anyhow, the close connection between civil society and academic movement makes degrowth an interesting case to apply a neo-Gramscian, socio-ecological transformation lens.

The degrowth movement has risen out of the contradictions of the hegemonic system. It has risen out of the hegemonic system’s inability to provide an economic compromise that responds to the contradictions. Degrowth exhibits the dialectics that are core to Gramsci’s philosophy of praxis (Femia, 1981). Without a period in which economic growth was hegemonic, degrowth would not exist (and if it did, it had no meaning). It is an expression of the historicity of the degrowth praxis and common sense. The task of the academic degrowth movement, amongst others, might be to translate common sense and praxis into a degrowth philosophy of praxis.

5.1. Degrowth through a neo-Gramscian lens

As noted Gramsci frames social change through the dialectic between practice and theory, between economic base and ideological superstructure (Femia, 1981). If

degrowth would only be an abstract academic discourse, it would have limited real-world relevance. It would not be able to respond to the challenges of people who struggle with the contradictions of the hegemonic system. It would not have answers to questions about degrowth in the global South or degrowth and unemployment. It is through the real-world applicability that theories gain relevance in a superstructural sense (Femia, 1981). If degrowth was only practiced, it would lack direction and would probably remain stuck. A problem discussed by degrowth scholars. Engler et al. (2024), analyzing 15 years of degrowth research, state that degrowth is viewed as too broad in its goals, objectives, and instruments. They find “[...] the lack of adequate discussion of concrete policy measures to achieve some of the central goals from the degrowth agenda is rather baffling” (Engler et al., 2024). A conclusion that was also found in an earlier analysis (Fitzpatrick et al., 2022). Degrowthers feel the need to provide the movement with direction and theorize about practice and common sense born out of the contradictions of the hegemonic system (Demaria et al., 2013; Fitzpatrick et al., 2022). The lack of a common strategy was taken up by the editors and authors of the book *Degrowth & Strategy: how to bring about social-ecological transformation* (Barlow et al., 2022). Thus, degrowth is both. It is praxis and philosophy. For degrowth to be successful, praxis and philosophy need to be combined in a degrowth philosophy of praxis.

5.1.1. Intellectuals of the degrowth movement

As pointed out, there is some criticism regarding the lack of direction of the degrowth movement. The degrowth movement, though, seems to be aware of this. Civil society, jointly with academics, works on this issue. At the Pontevedra Assembly 2024, civil society and academics convene to “[...] exchange on how best to collaborate and spread degrowth ideas, policies and practices” (International Degrowth Network, 2024). The 10th International Degrowth Conference “[...] seeks to deepen understanding and foster creativity around the key questions raised by the degrowth community. It provides a space for formulating strategies to mobilize this expanding field of knowledge production, driving societal transformation and addressing the accelerating eco-social crises” (Post-Growth Innovation Lab, 2024a). The book *Degrowth & Strategy* focuses on various pathways to bring about a transformation (Barlow et al., 2022). The book provides examples from praxis but also theorizes the transformation. The 2020 Degrowth Conference in Vienna was also dedicated to the topic of *Strategies for Social-Ecological Transformation*. The commentary (*Degrowth can work - here's how science can help*) by Hickel et al. (2022) further illustrates that degrowthers are aware of the strategic connection between the social movement and academic work. The book *Degrowth. A Vocabulary for a New Era* is yet another example of academics providing degrowth with conceptual structure and coherence by offering definitions of core terms (D'Alisa et al., 2014). A similar endeavor is degrowth.info, a webpage providing information about the movement and the degrowth concept (Rilović et al., 2022). The conclusion of the introductory chapter of the edition also underlines the relevance of academic work for the acceptance of degrowth.

“The future of degrowth is open. Research is still necessary to support foundational degrowth claims, claims that are firmly established *within* the degrowth community, providing its shared premises although they are far from being accepted by academia and society at large” (Kallis et al., 2014, p. 15).

Thus, the intellectuals of the movement not only work on understanding the themes of the movement (Demaria et al., 2013; Engler et al., 2024) but also on strategies that could render a transformation possible.

“All in all, the book [Degrowth & Strategy] is a step forward in thinking together with different degrowth initiatives and actors about how radical social-ecological transformation can be realized. By bringing degrowth in conversation with different other actors and movements fighting for social-ecological justice and equity, such as the climate justice movement, and providing concrete ways of engagement, I hope to see this book create ripples for change towards radical societal transformation towards justice and equity” (Barlow et al., 2022, p. 7)

The educational tasks of intellectuals need to be mentioned as well. As degrowth is a cultural revolution the role of the educational system is not negligible (Latouche, 2014). As indicated, on the one hand, degrowthers need to break out of the educational system that provided them formation. On the other hand, the education system itself can support a transformation by spreading alternative ideas. These aspects of education in the degrowth context are discussed by Kaufmann et al. (2019).

5.1.2. Degrowth fighting a war of positions

The war of positions implies that the degrowth movement *attacks* many fronts at the same time over a long period. This means that the movement has to collaborate with other movements, that it needs to uncover the flaws of the hegemonic system in various areas, and that it has to provide alternatives that are tied to the historical bloc that the degrowth movement is creating. Thus, much strategic thinking is required. And degrowthers seem to be aware of the strategies that they need to employ. For example, Schulken et al. (2022, p. 10) state that “[in] order to be effective, social movements have to confront the agendas driven by corporate and state actors, who have the power to ignore, water down, co-opt and criminalize transformative efforts.” They conclude that the degrowth movement needs a strategy “in the face of powerful actors who employ various strategies of their own to oppose change [...]” (Schulken et al., 2022, p. 16). Similarly, Brand (2022, p. 45) refers to “[...] a new critical orthodoxy [e.g. green growth] – a more or less radical change of the resource base of capitalism without transforming its cultural political economy and related logics of growth and power relations.” In the context of symbiotic transformation strategies Chertkovskaya (2022), points to the danger of counter-hegemonic views being coopted by the hegemonic system. These statements indicate the authors’ awareness of the hegemonic system’s strategies (passive revolution and *trasformismo*) that could hinder a transformation.

Degrowthers indicate the need to fight on multiple fronts and to unite different movements. Barlow et al. (2022, p. 8) point out that “[all] these pathways intersect and lead us into the same direction of a future based on justice, decolonialism and care for one another, based on the choice of limiting economic and social practices that are set up to destroy everyone.” On the one hand, this quote indicates that degrowthers understand that this is a multi-faceted war of positions and not a frontal attack (war of maneuver). On the other, it hints at the need to unite various movements under one umbrella.

The war of position is also fought within academia. Amongst others, this means that the ostensibly neutral field of economics needs to be (re)politicized (Kallis et al., 2014).

Funtowicz and Ravetz (1993) indicate that by portraying science as separate from society (i.e., depoliticization), it lost its ideological function. If we apply a Gramscian lens, one though understands that science only appears neutral as it follows the hegemonic ideology (Asara et al., 2015; Kaufmann et al., 2019). This makes a discourse between mainstream economics and alternatives difficult as the latter are portrayed as normative and thus non-scientific (Ciccotti et al., 1976; Gorz, 1976). Therefore, part of the war of positions is to also uncover the normativity of mainstream theories. Further, the war of positions within academia also means transforming the academic *industry* itself that has been shaped by the capitalistic growth-centered hegemonic system (Gorz, 1976).

5.1.3. Degrowth as a collaborative endeavor

It has been pointed out that one critical strategy of the hegemonic counter-movement is to unite several counter-movements. That is necessary, as the counter-hegemonic ideology needs to become universal (Im, 1991). The contradictions of the hegemonic system are not limited to economics, but include sexism, racism, environmental problems, etc. The counter-hegemonic movement needs to include all of these contradictions and provide better solutions that are tied to the new historical bloc (Im, 1991).

The collaboration among different counter-hegemonic movements is already taking place as several social movements find in degrowth a “common representative frame for their world view” (Demaria et al., 2013). Likewise, degrowthers see allies in counter-hegemonic movements that, while having different foci, also advocate for fundamental change (Schulken et al., 2022). “The degrowth vision of social-ecological transformation connects with a mosaic of progressive bottom-up movements across the world” (Schulken et al., 2022, p. 10). The need to organize multiple counter-hegemonic movements then also results in the urge to organize and strategize further action (Schulken et al., 2022).

Regarding plurality, Schulken et al. (2022) indicates that plurality is in itself not strategic, but that it can be. This leads back to the war of positions and the need to attack the hegemonic system on several fronts at the same time.

5.1.4. Degrowth as praxis

Using a practice theoretical lens, Brossmann and Islar (2020) analyze degrowth as transformative praxes within five areas: “(1) rethinking society, (2) acting political, (3) creating alternatives, (4) fostering connections, and (5) unveiling the self [...]” These five areas of living degrowth all contribute to a transformation. The categories overlap with the previous sections (5.1.1 - 5.1.3). While they can all be framed as praxis, this section only refers to what Brossmann and Islar (2020) call *creating alternatives*.

A core strategy to build a successful counter-hegemonic movement is to ground it in praxis. Thus, the alternative movement needs to provide actionable solutions to the contradictions of the hegemonic system. Clearly, the degrowth movement is deeply anchored in a social movement that practices alternatives. The book *Degrowth & Strategy* (Barlow et al., 2022) serves as an example. Part two of the book contains practical examples from food, housing, digitalization, energy, mobility, and more.

Apart from analyzing the practical alternatives that already exist, degrowthers also inquire how alternatives could attract those who are not easily convinced. “But one of our

most important challenges will be to practically demonstrate how walking that path of transformation will be beneficial for everyone in our societies beyond those already engaged” (Barlow et al., 2022, p. 8). This illustrates the awareness that degrowth must not be an academic exercise, detached from the struggles of the people. “We need to define not only the destination at the end of that path, but also be able to share with other people how to find the trailhead and get started in a very practical way” (Barlow et al., 2022, p. 8) Furthermore, degrowthers seem to be aware that the fundamental transformation they aspire involves a cultural change, which connects to practices (Latouche, 2014; Schulken et al., 2022, p. 17)

5.2. Degrowth and socio-ecological transition

Brand (2022, p. 42) states that “[degrowth is] about radical emancipatory social-ecological transformations “by design” – not “by disaster” – because the latter would likely imply a brutal shifting of the burden.” While the idea of designing or managing change might be palatable, it is questionable whether the fundamental transformation that the degrowth movement envisions can be designed (Smith et al., 2021). Socio-ecological transition theory indicates that due to the complexity of interconnected multi-scalar systems, it is difficult to plan change. As noted above (see Section 4), even if an alternative prepares well for the release and reorganization phase, no one can predict the outcome. The impossibility of predicting complex socio-ecological systems was also emphasized by Gramsci. As Gramsci opposed scientific Marxism, he did not believe that it would make sense to develop (natural) laws of change. He understood social life to be too complex to be predictable. Even if one could find patterns, it is not that these patterns are universally true.

“It follows that social change (and historical development) cannot be explained by reference to a formal system of causal laws beyond human intervention. [...] To begin with, by viewing all facts as a particular instance of abstract laws, they ignore the unique patterns and arrangements that emerged through the variations in social development. [...] Because their successful application depends upon recurrence and repetition of phenomena, cut-and-dried formulae and scientific techniques must, by definition, fail to embrace complex, contradictory and changing situations.” (Femia, 1981, p. 76)

While one might not be able to predict the future, Gramsci still saw value in studying past transformations to draw lessons for future dynamics (Femia, 1981). Thus, while we cannot design the transformation, we can take steps to trigger it and prepare for a *favorable* outcome.

In reference to the adaptive cycle, one can thus, not plan when and how the release phase is reached. However, one can trigger it and prepare for the release. The preparation lies in the strategies listed above (Section 5.1.). These strategies provide the seeds for a new start. Furthermore, it needs to be highlighted that the role of pushing the system over its tipping point will be decisive (see Figure 8). The earlier the degrowth movement manages to tip the system, the better. The longer a system remains stuck in one state the more devastating the release phase. An example, from ecology are wildfires. Small fires are less destructive than one big fire, as is hotter and more destructive (Gunderson & Holling, 2002, chapter 8). We can also take this insight from IPCC scenarios where the change becomes more difficult the longer we wait taking the needed measures to reduce

emissions (IPCC, 2023). Thus, as strange as it might sound, the role of counter-hegemonic movements is to make the system tip earlier. Though, it can be argued that this cannot and should not be rushed either. To get civil society on board large-scale disillusionment needs to take place. The contradictions of the hegemonic system need to be apparent to a large number of people. Further, the attempts to address these contradictions through economic compromises need to be unsuccessful. The degrowth movement can help to uncover that offered economic compromises and superstructural ideologies are only a *trick*¹³. As pointed out this requires analysis and the use of scientific as well as popular language, symbols, and communication streams. Therefore, the collaboration between academic and non-academic degrowthers is key.

Part of the transformation path is that the economic compromise is unsuccessful. Accordingly, people have to go through a challenging time of disillusionment to distance themselves from the hegemonic system (Smith et al., 2021). Brand (2022, p. 55) argues that the degrowth movement has to “block the destructive components of existing social life and related interests.” I would caution against this strategy. The degrowth movement has to illustrate the destructiveness and provide alternatives. As mentioned, the war of positions is a dialectic of destruction and creation. The degrowth movement would not exist without the destructive character of the hegemonic system. Rather than stopping the destruction, the counter-hegemonic movement needs to flag it and provide solutions that are bound to the historical bloc it is building (Im, 1991). In this respect, the degrowth movement needs to be cautious that the offered solutions are not appropriated by the hegemonic system. Thus, the hegemonic system must be blocked from successfully employing strategies such as *transformismo* and *passive revolution* inspired by solutions offered by the degrowth movement.

When the masses distance themselves from the hegemonic system, it will get closer to the release phase. At that point, it will be important that the degrowth movement is mature (approaching or in the K phase). The maturity of the movement is captured by the axis of the active cycle; network and potential. As outlined in section 5.1, the degrowth movement actively works on increasing both variables. It seeks connections within its own movement but also with other counter-hegemonic movements. Potentiality increases by the growing network but also by the movement’s strong connection to praxis. The practical solutions that the degrowth movement offers represent powerful seeds of change, increasing the movement’s overall potentiality.

Timing is decisive. Although Gramsci thought that a war of positions is necessary for a transformation of modern democratic systems, he did not exclude the possibility of a war of maneuver at some point in the transformative process. Strictly speaking, the war of maneuver involves military forces. However, for the purpose of this paper, it shall be framed as a frontal attack in a metaphorical sense. A frontal attack by the degrowth movement will only be successful if the war of positions is already won. In that sense, a frontal attack can represent the last push to tip the system. Thus, a frontal attack should not be executed before the hegemonic system is not on the verge of tipping into the release phase.

¹³ E.g. uncovering that the inverted U narrative does not hold true, that wealth does not just trickle down, that relative decoupling is not enough, etc.

Finally, we can hypothesize about the reorganization phase. Potentially, several alternatives will try to profit from the system collapse. Gramsci's analysis of the socialist revolution illustrates that (Morton, 2018). Instead of a socialist system a fascist system took power over. In recent years right-wing politics has gained momentum. Thus, the repetition of such dynamics cannot be ruled out in the future (Büchs & Koch, 2019). Several aspects will influence the success of an alternative in the reorganization phase. First, the alternative needs to survive the release phase in good state. Hypothetically, there could be multiple severe crises related to climate change, biodiversity loss, food shortages, military conflict, etc. Not only the current hegemonic system might collapse, but likely the alternatives will too. We must not forget that the Panarchy represents a suite of nested systems, which are all connected. Thus, a crisis needs to be severe enough for the current system to be released, but not too severe to also substantially harm the alternative. Once the crisis hits, the success of alternatives will depend on their state. Are they still well connected? Can they still build on their potential? And how does one alternative compete with others in these respects? The importance of preparing the seeds, building networks, and fostering potential will play out in the reorganization phase.

6. Concluding remarks

The degrowth movement is an interesting case to study the application of neo-Gramscian thought about the role of intellectuals in transformation processes. Intellectuals are presented as translators between ideological superstructure and common sense. As organic intellectuals academics subscribe to and advocate for a specific ideology. They can help civil society to synthesize common sense into a coherent, structured ideology that can challenge the hegemonic ideology. Intellectuals can support in navigating ideological discourses as they are acquainted with the dominant symbols and language. By introducing alternative views into the education system, academics can help to proliferate alternative ideas. At the same time, academics can help to uncover the inconsistencies of the hegemonic system and develop actionable solutions to problems these inconsistencies create. Organic intellectuals can support strategizing and finding allies. All of these aspects can be found in the degrowth movement.

The article also makes use of socio-ecological transition theory. This theory helps not only to understand that transformations are complex, which likely cannot be planned or designed. However, the adaptive cycle gives insights regarding timing and factors relevant in transformation processes. For example, it was highlighted that the hegemonic system needs to be close to the release phase, while the alternative needs to have matured enough to increase the likelihood of determining the characteristics of the new system. The manuscript also offers an adapted illustration of the adaptive cycle to better understand the nestedness of systems and the continuous dynamics along the transformation process.

A final thought about the transformation towards a degrowth system relates to overcoming hegemony itself. Arguably degrowth has the potential to accomplish this, as it strives to maintain the autonomy of actors and as it cherishes flat hierarchies. However, degrowthers are aware that danger lies in strategizing to achieve a transformation and maintaining a movement that is built on the rejection of hegemony (Rilović et al., 2022;

Schulken et al., 2022). It will remain interesting to observe if and how the ex-ante thought experiment of a socio-ecological transformation towards degrowth will unfold.

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